

Developing Algebraic Concepts among Umm Al-Qura University Students Using Electronic Platforms According to the Quality Criteria and their Effect on Habits of the Mind and the Transmission of Learning

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Abstract

The aim of the research was to identify (technological, technical, humanistic, training, organizational, administrative and educational) requirements, the degree of their importance, availability to activate electronic platforms, the specialists' attitudes on activating their use in teaching according to the Quality Criteria and its effect on the development of algebraic concepts and habits of mind among university students. First, identifying electronic platforms, their applications and advantages in teaching and learning algebraic concepts. Second, piloting teaching staff's opinions, mathematics section at university and its branches to identify electronic educational platforms in teaching and learning algebraic concepts from their points of view. Third, spotting the light on the difficulties faced by students, mathematics section, Umm Al-Qura University when applying electronic platforms program in teaching and learning. Fourth, identifying the effect of demographic factors when applying electronic platforms in teaching and learning algebraic concepts. Fifth, determining the importance of developing algebraic concepts and its effect on the habits of mind. The procedures of the research were: (1) theoretical background spotted the light on the results of previous experiments, applications and researches conducted in high education institutions, both Arab and international universities on electronic educational platforms in addition to topics related to the current research regarding to algebraic concepts and habits of the mind. (2) Field study: preparing a test of algebraic concepts, a scale of habits of mind on three -Likert Scale (Agree- To Somewhat Agree- Disagree), and a test of learning transmission on a sample (445) students, mathematics section, Umm Al-Qura University, first and second term, 2019/2020. Finally, analyzing data on SPSS V25, interpreting results, presenting recommendations and suggestions such as preparing electronic techniques for various subjects, especially educational activities for applying program and developing them.

Introduction

The world has witnessed knowledgeable and technological developments during recent times in all life fields. This evokes the concern to recent models and directives which present ideas that develop the society and deal with challenges that face their individuals. This can be through what educational courses presented for learners in mathematics section in different educational stages. This helps develop their abilities in facing situations and solve future problems through suitable ways.

The different rapid technological developments in different fields, knowledge and scientific development direct educational institutions to review their educational plans and strategies and working on blending recent techniques in educational organization. Thus, if the rate of change inside each educational institution was lower than the rate of change outside it, this institution wouldn't cope up with scientific and technological developments. It requires harnessing scientific and technological developments for the benefit of the educational process (Welch, 2007).

Thus, electronic learning is used to support and provide the regular learning process, using technologies and new electronic tools. It facilitates the learning process in an active and effective manner, in addition to enhance its performance, and increase its effectiveness by providing access to information in more than one way and style. As a result of the efforts made, educational platforms have emerged with complete storage areas. They combine multiple libraries that benefit in developing the use of the Internet in one software package. It makes easy for Internet programmers to use it to take advantages of these applications in the educational process, including electronic educational platforms (Stratakis et al., 2003). The electronic educational platforms provide a number of benefits to the educational process, through their characteristics and components, which are

highlighted by providing the ability to browse the Internet, in addition to provide access to the total network, and the ability to use e-mail to join the platform. The electronic educational platform is considered as an educational network, and it is an easy way to exchange information, ideas and educational concepts. It also provides an opportunity to view the work of student groups. In addition to the ease of communication and evaluation of the faculty member with his students, it contributes to change the teaching method, making it more effective through interactive courses, and social communication (Ivers & Barron, 2002). Based on what has been tackled about the importance and role of electronic learning in the educational process in general, and the role of electronic educational platforms in particular, the researchers believe that employing technological tools in various educational fields contributes to the development of this process and increases its effectiveness. Therefore, it is imperative to work to harness various energies and efforts by those in charge of developing the educational process, and related teaching methods and strategies, with the aim of increasing the effectiveness of educational inputs, especially in the university education stage. This aims at achieving educational outputs, represented by competencies capable of keeping pace with the scientific and knowledgeable development. Thus, it is best to provide students with the opportunity to obtain information in more than one way, and in more than one style, especially what is related to mathematics, in the light of the students' need to develop their abilities and information, and increase their skills in the field of mathematics. These aspects can be achieved by employing modern technology tools, foremost of which are electronic educational platforms.

Habits of the mind are considered behavioral patterns that are related to the cognitive structure of the learner. Kattami and Arnaki (2007) emphasized the importance of its learning and developing among the learner, as it will ultimately lead to meaningful learning outcomes. Also, Costa and Calik, (2003) noted that mental habits help employ knowledge and produce new ideas that facilitate the learning process, and also help in learner's self-regulation during achieving the task. Because of the importance of developing the habits of mind among university students and practicing them, educational institutions must work according to the Quality Criteria, and integrate the habits of mind into the curriculum and provide daily opportunities by encouraging learning for today and tomorrow. It focuses on the partnership between the institution and the local community to achieve the highest benefit from the potential of learners. Due to the importance of the habits of the mind, the United States of America has directed the preparation of the scientific culture project 2061, which focuses on developing the cognitive construction of the learner and supporting it in order to obtain meaningful learning (Ali, 2015). Some studies emphasized the great importance of habits of mind, and some studies have found the need to work on developing them using different teaching strategies (Zidan, 2005; Morgan, 2015; Mahdi, 2017). Marzano et al. (2000) noted that the habits of the mind were weak, regardless of the degree of the learner's knowledge, or his level of performance. Many individuals collect knowledge and skills in a specific topic but do not know how to behave when they encounter new situations. The problem was not a deficiency in the skill or ability, but the matter was simply that they gave up and stopped working when the answers and solutions were not readily available, and this in turn made skillful learners ineffective ones if they did not develop the habits of mind.

Whoever contemplates mathematics curricula finds that it is still focused on knowledge for its own sake with little interest in employing it to produce new ideas for learners. This leads to lose this knowledge, its importance and value, in addition to form negative attitudes toward its learning and low achievement. Due to the importance of mathematics, specialists made many efforts to develop teaching and keep pace with these developments and changes. Modern trends of its teaching have focused on developing conceptual knowledge, assimilating it to students, building it meaningfully in the student's cognitive structure and using it in new situations, developing thinking and positive attitudes towards the subject and increasing its achievement (Al-Azzawi & Nasser, 2011).

The process of renewal and modernization in the field of mathematics teaching strategies in the modern era is no longer controversy or discussion, but rather has become a matter of great importance and a vital or urgent requirement in order to bring a balance between a rapidly changing life in the era of globalization. As traditional education faced many problems that had an impact on the level of education in general, and made it fall short of achieving its goals. Traditional mathematics teaching strategies were unable to keep pace with a modern era full of challenges and rapid changes. Therefore, the need is for teaching strategies that are more effective, and more sensitive to the needs and preferences of students (Saleh, 2012).

By reviewing previous studies and literature that tackled the habits of the mind, most of them emphasized that there was no concern among students, and the real context of teaching mathematics in the educational institutions, it was found that it focused on providing knowledge and information ready for students, and teaching relied on direct presentation that motivates students to memorize. This in turn lead to students' lack of habits of mind skills.

There were many studies that confirmed the weakness in habits of mind among students, and various teaching activities were used, such as study of Younis and Allam (2016) which aimed to determine the level of habits of mind through the teaching process of 70 students, and the level of mental habits reached 54.6%, which is a low percentage. Also, the study of Abdul Aziz (2015), which aimed to develop mathematical skills and habits of mind in mathematics, and recommended employing the habits of the mind in the educational process. According

to the study of Hussam Al-Din (2008), the study of Steinkuehler and Duncan (2008), which used a group of edutainment games presented over the Internet to develop twelve habits of the scientific mind, and the study of Al-Qahtani (2014) that used the model of Learning dimensions for the subject of algebra in developing the habits of productive mind among the top/superior students in schools of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, The problem was felt through:

First: The reality of using technology tools in the educational process.

The reality of using technology tools in the educational process faced multiple obstacles, and the overall obstacles were related to the use of technology tools could be summarized in the following aspects (Al-Naabi, 2010):

- The curricula are not designed in a way that helps employ technology tools, allow the staff and the student to access knowledge sources and be unaware of them.
- The absence of a clear channel that contributes to the compatibility of the curricula in terms of linking the various sources of knowledge.
- Lack of training in the concepts of teaching design, and how to use technology tools within the framework of the concept of educational technology, and training is limited to basic skills in the use of computers.
- The lack of an infrastructure planned to accommodate the technological changes of continuous and rapid developments, due to the lack of clarity of the future vision of the concept of using technology tools, and their effect on improving the learning and education process.

Al-Dabaa and Gaballah (2002) pointed out many obstacles for using technology tools in the educational process, the most prominent of which are the following:

- The absence of precise determination of the goals of using technology tools in education, and there wasn't a specific plan to employ them in educational situations.
- The need for training on the multiple uses of technology tools, and the skills to use and deal with them.
- The need to equip classrooms with modern tools and devices, as these classrooms lack many of the elements for using technology tools.

Rodney (2002) noted that the most important obstacles to use technology tools in teaching were through the lack of effective leadership and appropriate training for it, in addition to the lack of necessary tools and equipment, as well as the lack of technical support for this type of education, in addition to the weakness of the necessary infrastructure.

Second: A pilot study was carried out by the two researchers observing the teaching performance of (10) members of the teaching staff in mathematics, through which it was found:

- 90% of the faculty members relied on strategies, methods and approaches that depended on transferring knowledge and neglecting thinking skills.
- Faculty members rarely viewed consciously the activities to help students use the habits of mind, but the emphasis was merely on teaching educational content.

Third: The two researchers conducted open interviews with some faculty members with the aim of knowing the extent of their awareness of electronic educational platforms and the concept of habits of mind in mathematics and how to benefit from them in teaching, and the following became clear:

- Most of staff had a low knowledge level in using educational e-platforms and they don't identify the concept of habits of the mind in mathematics.
- 15% guessed their answers which were wrong.
- 10% guessed their answers which were somewhat right.

Fourth: reviewing educational conferences, literature and previous studies in the field of habits of the mind and algebraic concepts, and the use of electronic educational platforms indicated how education should be, and recommended employing platforms and developing habits of mind in the educational process.

From what has mentioned above, it is evident that there was a low level in algebraic concepts and habits of mind among mathematics students at Umm Al-Qura University. According to the scientific and educational importance of electronic educational platforms, their association with the habits of mind and concepts of algebra, the current research is an attempt to study the effectiveness of using electronic platforms in teaching according to the Quality Criteria and their impact on developing concepts of algebra, habits of mind, and transferring the impact of learning among students of Umm Al-Qura University. The research problem emerges in light of the rapid technological development that touched the various fields of the educational process, especially teaching methods and strategies, In light of this development, many strategies and methods of distance learning and electronic learning emerged, which imposed many challenges on all educational institutions, especially institutions of higher education.

Consequently, the research problem appears through the ability of these institutions to keep pace with technological developments, and to employ their innovations in the educational process, and among these innovations are electronic educational platforms and the reality of using these platforms in teaching the algebra course at Umm Al-Qura University. There is a need to use them in the Saudi university educational

environment. In light of the above, the researchers found the desire and motivation to tackle the reality of using electronic educational platforms in teaching algebra from the point of view of faculty members at Umm Al-Qura University in addition to the weakness of the habits of mind and concepts of algebra among mathematics students at Umm Al-Qura University. To overcome the problem, the current research is an attempt to answer the following main question: “What is the effectiveness of using e-platforms in teaching algebra according to the quality criteria and their impact on developing the concepts, habits of mind and transmission of learning effect among Umm Al-Qura University students?”, This question is divided into the following sub-questions:

1. What is the proposed conception of a program based on electronic educational platforms in teaching Algebra to develop the habits of mind and concepts included in the course among mathematics section students at Umm Al-Qura University?
2. What is the effectiveness of electronic educational platforms in developing the habits of mind among mathematics section students at Umm Al-Qura University?
3. What is the effectiveness of electronic educational platforms in developing algebra concepts among mathematics section students at Umm Al-Qura University?
4. What is the effectiveness of electronic educational platforms in transmitting the impact of learning among mathematics section students at Umm Al-Qura University?

1. Research framework

The aims of theoretical framework were:

- The habits of the mind, its definition, characteristics, principles and requirements, its importance, and development.
- Electronic educational platforms, their definition, importance, and obstacles to their use.

Thus, Theoretical Framework tackled the following pillars:

1.1. *The habits of the mind*

Habit is something that the individual performs repeatedly without effort, and when developed countries used this concept in the process of teaching and learning, and combined it with the mind and its capabilities, they produced a new concept, which is the habit of the mind. The interest in and development of these habits are one of the main goals of education, with the aim of producing capable learners to use their skills and mental capabilities, taking into account the continuous application of quality standards in their working life.

2.1.1 *Definition of Habits of Mind*

Habits of mind are among the modern concepts in the field of contemporary education. The opinions and attitudes of specialists in determining what they are, have differed according to their different perspectives, specializations and attitudes towards it. Several interpretations appeared, for example, Costa and Kallick (2008) defined them as the ability of the individual to confront a confusing situation or an ambiguous question, the interpretation of which is not clear in the mental structure. This means that the habits of the mind implicitly refer to the employment of intelligent behavior when the individual does not know the appropriate answer or solution. As for Allen (2017), they are the learning outcomes that help the individual reach his learning performance, based on the set of experiences acquired when confronted with a complex situation or confusing question, in order to reach mental and performance results.

From the above, it is clear that the habits of the mind are nothing but conscious and continuous stereotypes that appear to confront a problem using mental strategies based on knowledge, attitude and values, leading to a productive act to achieve a desired goal.

2.1.2 *Characteristics of Habits of Mind*

The characteristics of the habits of mind are: (Allen, 2017 & Goldenberg et al., 2015)

- A mixture of skills, attitudes, experiences and tendencies possessed by the learner.
- It indicates that we prefer one type of intellectual behavior over other patterns, and therefore it implies making choices about which patterns should be used at a certain time and no other patterns.
- It requires a high level of skill to use, and maintain performances effectively.
- Reflect on the level of progress to complete the task, evaluate, amend, and advance it towards future applications.

Hence, adopting habits of the mind seeks the learner to progress towards the accomplishment of the task by making use of previous experiences and requirements employing appropriate performances for the situation in an effective manner in addition to the final evaluation each time for improvement and modification.

2.1.3 *Principles and Requirements of Habits of Mind*

Sulia and Kumjian (2017), and Conway and Eckersley (2017) indicated that there are four main rules or principles that emerge from cognitive researches, which emphasize the need to develop habits of the mind, and these principles call for making thinking and teaching processes more accessible by relying on cognitive structures. Mind-enhancing requirements are:

- Organizing knowledge among students.
- Building on the students' knowledge.
- Preparing and processing information.

- Facilitate deep thinking and make it clear.

2.1.4 The importance of Students' Acquisition of Habits of Mind

The importance of developing habits of mind is as follows (Sulia & Kumjian, 2017):

- Students acquire useful habits in practical life, such as evaluation, reflection and perseverance.
- Helping students acquire the ability to blend the capabilities of thinking and self-organization of performance processes.
- Selecting the appropriate performance for the problem faced by the learner.
- Providing the opportunity for students to see their own thinking and discover how the mind works while solving problems
- Encouraging students to have the will to use mental capabilities in all educational and life activities, so that thinking becomes a habit for the student that he does not be tired of practicing.
- Helping the student to plan accurately in light of the requirements of the task he is performing, and according to quality standards to evaluate his performance in light of it.

Habits of the mind are of great importance in the educational process in general, then they are more important in mathematics in particular. Obaida (2011) explained that habits of the mind are the ways students think about the mathematical content and are related to a set of smart activities for students while learning content and building mathematical knowledge.

Among the recent trends in mathematics teaching are the following (Anusha, 2017):

- Teaching mathematics in order to develop different thinking skills and habits of mind among students.
- Developing the habits of the mind is considered an entry point for developing mathematics.
- Emphasizing on enjoying studying mathematics, which increases motivation towards learning it.
- Focusing on modern technologies and teaching activities in the field of mathematics.
- Identifying the requirements (technological- technical - human - training - organizational - administrative - educational) and the degree of their importance, the extent of the availability of these requirements necessary to activate the electronic platforms, and the trends of specialists on activating the use of electronic educational platforms in teaching in accordance with Quality Criteria.
- Developing the habits of the mind that helps the awareness of the learner's thinking paths and their awareness at the level of feeling, strengthens or modifies them, and increases his management of thinking, organization, perseverance and his ability to modify his behavior patterns.

2.1.5 Developing Habits of Mind in Mathematics

The development of habits of mind among students is one of the recent trends related to teaching, as it is the product of the interaction between the student's will and his mental skills. The importance of developing habits of the mind is a set of behaviors that transfer the student from preserving knowledge to building and producing knowledge.

Some literature and studies, including Obaida (2011), Costa and Calik (2003), emphasized the importance of developing habits of mind among students and the interest in integrating them into the cognitive content during planning, and then developing them through various teaching activities. This will lead to change many practices and beliefs. Concerning the teaching and learning processes, Costa and Calik (2003) indicated several directives for a faculty member to implement habits in the field of mathematics, including the following:

- Ask students to think about a non-mathematical problem they encountered. Ask them to describe how they solved it? With mentioning at least two other methods that they could have solved through them.
- Have students compare and contrast the concepts they have learned (use several methods to solve the problem).
- Assign students to explain any algebraic concepts they have learned.
- Ask students, after they finish a project, to evaluate it, what skills and concepts did they have to use? What did they learn from completing the project? What habits of mind did they use? How did they use it?

There were many studies that dealt with developing habits of the mind and the importance of acquiring them to students in mathematics, including Berrett's (2012) that the true value of university education is the development of habits of mind among students that affect their thinking for years after graduation and make them seek deep and lasting learning for life. Calik's (2012) prepared a reliable tool for exploring the scientific habits of mind among science teachers with diverse scientific backgrounds. She recommended using the tool with other groups to reveal the habits of mind they have.

The study of Hazard (2013) indicated the need to develop habits of mind among new students in universities so that they can meet the academic, intellectual, emotional and social challenges that they face at the beginning of their enrollment in the college and adapt to the academic requirements of the college and push them to attitudes and mindsets that lead them to the transition to effective learning.

Çalik et al. (2013) aimed to measure the scientific habits of mind among student teachers when discussing sociological issues, and compare this with academic performance and the type of program they studied. The sample consisted of 1,600 students, teachers of science, mathematics, and social sciences. In need of

development to help students develop better habits of scientific mind if they are to participate more effectively in the decision-making process and discuss sociological issues in their classes.

By reviewing the results of previous studies, all of them emphasized the importance of developing habits of mind to face academic and cultural challenges and the adaptation that we face in the future with its requirements.

1.2. Electronic Educational Platforms

In light of the technological development, e-learning has clearly emerged in various educational institutions, foremost of which is a higher education institution, as many universities have used it to develop the educational process, and to support the trend towards e-learning in Saudi universities. As some universities have evaluated many courses with the aim of providing tools and strategies that contribute to the service of these courses and the development of the educational process. Among the electronic educational tools, the use of electronic educational platforms has emerged as a tool that can be used in the educational process, especially at the university level. This approach has been adopted by a number of universities, and these tools have been used in the service of curricula and courses.

In light of the rapid technological developments in various fields, the scientific and cognitive development, various educational institutions must reconsider educational plans and strategies, and work to integrate modern technologies into the educational system. Thus, the rate of change inside the educational institution is less than the rate of change outside it. This institution will not be able to keep pace with scientific and technological developments, which requires harnessing scientific and technological developments for the benefit of the educational process (Welch, 2007).

And there are many universities that have adopted and used several types of electronic educational tools. So, the traditional role of universities has changed in light of the scientific and technological development, and these universities have become more open, and have adopted open programs, integrated programs, as well as virtual programs for some courses, in a manner consistent with education. The usual process is through the integration in the programs that they offer, and therefore the use of electronic educational will be used naturally, and it will no longer be a special and separate thing from the existing learning and teaching system, but rather it has become an essential element, and it will be an integrated part with it.

Educational institutions have dealt with e-learning as one of the basics of the education process, as its addition to the educational process has gained the education system strategic importance, especially in the university education stage, with the aim of developing patterns of regular education through the use of available educational technology, facilitating students' learning process, and providing communication opportunities. And the interaction between the various parties of the educational process, and increasing its effectiveness (More & Pinhey, 2006).

2.2.1 The Concept of Electronic Educational Platforms

Electronic educational platform is used to provide and support the normal learning process, using technologies and electronic tools by providing some electronic content and communication capabilities. This type may not affect the workflow of regular lectures, but rather enhances their performance, and contributes to increasing their effectiveness by providing access on the information in more than one way.

As a result of the efforts that have been made, educational platforms have emerged with complete storage areas that combine multiple libraries and benefit in developing the use of the Internet in one software package. This makes it easier for Internet programmers to use it to take advantage of these applications in the educational process, including electronic educational platforms (Stratakis, 2003).

Many definitions of educational platform have been mentioned. Mei (2012) defined it as: a distance learning network based on cognitive technology for the web, which is a safe environment for the exchange of educational content and its practical applications as an integrated educational environment. Karrar (2012) defined it as a multimedia platform that contains two screens, a control screen, a touch screen, and a display screen that displays its content on a smart board or computer.

Based on what has been covered of the definitions of the educational platform, researchers can point out that the educational platform is one of the tools of modern technology that can be used in many areas of the educational process with the aim of facilitating the education process in light of the characteristics and features it provides that help in this field

2.2.2 The Importance of Electronic Educational Platforms

The electronic educational platforms provide a number of benefits to the educational process, through their characteristics and components, which are highlighted by providing the ability to browse the Internet, in addition to providing access to the total network, and the ability to use e-mail to enter the platform.

There are many advantages of educational platforms obtained when using the platform in education. These benefits are evident by increasing students' interaction, developing their scientific and cognitive abilities, in addition to increasing students' motivation towards learning and cooperative work, as well as facilitating the role of the faculty member during the educational process. Additionally, it increases the efficiency of the faculty member, improving the level and quality of learning, and increasing interaction during academic lectures

between students and the academic subject, and between students and faculty members by opening frameworks for dialogue and discussion about the academic subjects (Weingardt, 2004).

The role of electronic educational platform is highlighted through the educational contributions they provide for the various academic levels and academic courses. As these platforms provide students with various information that can contribute to raise their level of achievement, in addition to develop their perceptions, and increase their educational attainment in various domains.

The electronic educational platforms are considered as an educational network, and it is an easy way to exchange information and ideas about educational content, and it also provides an opportunity to see the work of student groups, in addition to the ease of teacher communication with his students, as well as measuring the level of students and seeing the tasks assigned to them, and using web tools. Contribute to changing the teaching method, making it more effective through its reliance on interactive courses and social communication (Ivers and Barron, 2002).

There is also an online educational platform "AWARENESS", which is an initiative of the Queen Rania Foundation for Education and Development. It is an Arab open education platform that works to provide education opportunities for all, free of charge for all ages and groups without restrictions or conditions, without prejudice to race or age, and is interested in providing opportunities Learning is especially for those who do not have access to information through specialized university studies. "AWARENESS" displays specialized university educational materials through interactive methods and methods, and by using multimedia to transform learning into an enjoyable process (Al-Mallah, 2010).

Among the Arab educational platforms is the (RIWAQ), which is an Arab platform for open education, for all ages, and this platform aims to provide information and knowledge in various disciplines, and works within the team of the RIWAQ platform specialists seeking to expand the circle of beneficiaries of information and knowledge, through Free academic study materials in the Arabic language in various fields and disciplines, provided by distinguished academics from around the Arab world, and through video lectures and interactive participations.

The researchers believed that the role of electronic tools, including educational platforms, emerges through the benefits they provide that can contribute to the development of the educational process. They achieve positive coping with the uses of these tools, and use them in the service of various academic courses, including mathematics education.

Mallareddy (2013) believed that the importance of using electronic tools in education in general lies in the following aspects:

- Achieving learning most of the time by addressing barriers of time and space.
- Addressing the shortage of faculty staff by using virtual classrooms and educational platforms.
- Providing the opportunity for students to record and review academic lectures.
- Saving time, effort and financial costs.
- Helping teaching methods in line with scientific and technological development.

Prensky (2006) noted that the importance of using electronic tools in education lies in the following aspects:

- Electronic tools contribute to providing the best opportunities for interaction between the learner and the subject, and between learners and teachers.
- Providing an educational environment that contributes to acquiring information and knowledge in a more positive way.
- Providing students with an opportunity to learn about other cultures.
- Since mathematics is an important part of the concept of globalization, it helps to enhance communication with others in various societies. It has become increasingly necessary to integrate electronic tools into its teaching among the factors that encourage students to become more involved in the education process to achieve learning goals.
- Based on what has been discussed about the importance and role of e-learning in the educational process in general and the role of educational platforms in particular, the researchers believe that employing technological tools in various educational fields contributes to the development of this process and increases its effectiveness. Therefore, it is imperative to work on harnessing the various energies and efforts of those in charge of developing the educational process, and the associated teaching methods and strategies, with the aim of increasing the effectiveness of educational inputs, especially in the university education stage, with the aim of reaching educational outputs, represented by competencies capable of keeping pace with scientific and cognitive development. Therefore, it is necessary to work to provide students with the opportunity to obtain Information in more than one way, and in more than one method, especially what is related to mathematics. These aspects can be achieved through the use of modern technology tools, foremost of which are electronic educational platforms.

There are many studies that identified the degree of use of electronic educational platforms in the education process, including the study Younei and Leask (2013) in Britain aimed at revealing the degree of use of electronic educational platforms in schools and universities in Britain, and their role in the educational process.

In order to achieve the objectives of the study, the inductive approach was used, by reviewing the records and data of (12) electronic educational platform affiliated with the British Communication Agency for Education and Technology. The results of the study showed that teachers need continuous professional development in terms of increasing their knowledge of electronic educational platforms in terms of technical and educational. However, this support and training is not available in times of need in schools, while it is available in universities permanently. The results of the study also showed that there are obstacles facing teachers in their practice of the educational process through electronic educational platforms, such as operating problems and lack of knowledge of management information systems. Thus, there was a positive role for the use of electronic educational platforms in increasing student participation, information exchange, and increasing student motivation.

Benta et al. (2014) in Romania aimed at identifying the effect of using electronic educational platforms in developing and activating the education process and participating in tasks. To achieve the objectives of the study, the service center records, which were collected from electronic educational platforms, were used and analyzed, which reached (2970) records for a period of three months. Most famously, special courses were used to learn using the educational platforms. The sample of the study consisted of (202) male and female university students, who were divided into two groups, experimental and control. The experimental group consisted of (98) students, who were taught using the electronic educational platform, and they received special courses to learn how to use it, and the control group consisted of (104) male and female students. They were taught using the regular method. The results of the study showed a statistically significant difference of the electronic educational platform in motivating students and increasing their participation in cognitive tasks. The results confirmed the existence of a difference in students' achievement and performance in their academic tasks, in favor of the Experimental group that studied on the e-learning platform.

Stergioulas et al. (2014) conducted a study in the United Kingdom aimed at exploring the use of online educational platforms and their impact on the learning process. The study sample consisted of (82) male and female students, who were distributed into an experimental group that studied using electronic learning platforms, and a control group that studied using the standard method. In order to achieve the objectives of the study and collect data, a test was conducted in the subject of Information and Communication Technology to reveal the effect of the platforms and the nature of their use. The results of the study showed the easiness of using electronic educational platforms, and the results also showed the existence of a statistically significant positive effect of electronic educational platforms on the learning process, and raising the level of students' performance in various scientific activities and tasks, and increased positive interaction.

2.2.3 Barriers/Obstacles of Using Electronic Educational Platforms

Given the reality of using technology tools in the educational process in general, it did not reach up to the desired level and serious practical application, due to the lack of a framework and implementation mechanism that takes into account the reality of the field. Despite the interest in using technology tools in teaching, there are some obstacles that may limit their use, which may appear through the lack of possession of educational competencies with the help of technology tools, the increase in the tasks required of those in charge of the educational process, the density of the curriculum, the incompatibility of the curriculum with the use of technology tools, in addition to the lack of readiness of the infrastructure, the limited number of computers, their inconsistency with the numbers of students, and the lack of qualified human cadres, supervisors, and specialists in employing technology tools in the educational process as required (Al-Otaibi, 2009).

The process of employing technology tools also faces some obstacles, whether at the level of administration, material cost, or training, and thus the need for employment appears according to a model that helps solve the problems facing its application, as some limited models have been used to employ technology tools (Jibreen, 2004). The reality of using technology tools in the educational process faces multiple obstacles, and the overall obstacles related to the use of technology tools can be summarized in the following aspects: (Al-Naabi, 2010):

- The curricula are not designed in a way that helps to employ technology tools, to allow the faculty member and the student to access knowledge sources and be unaware of them.
- The absence of a clear channel that contributes to the compatibility of the curricula in terms of linking the various sources of knowledge.
- Lack of training in teaching design concepts, and how to use technology tools within the framework of the concept of educational technology, and training is limited to basic computer skills.
- The absence of an infrastructure planned to accommodate the technological changes of continuous and rapid development, due to the lack of clarity of the future vision of the concept of using technology tools, and their effect on improving the learning and education process.

Al-Dabaa and Gaballah (2002) pointed out many obstacles for using technology tools in the educational process, the most prominent of which are the following:

- The absence of precise definition of the goals of using technology tools in education, and the absence of a specific plan to employ them in situations.
- The need for training on the multiple uses of technology tools, and the skills for their use and handling.

- The need to equip classrooms with modern tools and devices, as these classrooms lack many of the elements for using technology tools.

Rodney (2002) noted that the most important obstacles to use technology tools in teaching arise through the lack of effective leadership and appropriate training for it, in addition to the lack of necessary tools and equipment, as well as the lack of technical support for this type of education, in addition to the weakness of the necessary infrastructure.

Al-Muhaisen (2006) believed that one of the most important obstacles to the use of modern technology tools is the wide gap between the theoretical and practical side in the preparation and qualification programs about the use of teaching methods based on modern technology because of the separation between theory and practice. Therefore, modern trends in preparation programs should focus on develop technology in addition to the introduction of the principle of linking theory and practice, by employing and applying theoretical information in practical reality.

The researchers believed that there was a wide gap resulting from the fact that many models that tried in various ways to overcome some of the obstacles facing the integration of electronic learning media in the educational process led to a distancing from using the concept of technology that contributes to building educational and educational policies and plans. Thus, there is an urgent need to review the concept of technology and formulate it so that it contributes to solve educational problems in an era that witnessed the momentum of knowledge.

2. Aim and hypotheses

From the background presented above, it is relatively designed a program based on electronic educational platforms in teaching algebra to develop the habits of mind and concepts included in the course among mathematics section students .Identifying (technological, technical, humanistic, training, organizational, administrative and educational) requirements and the degree of their importance, the extent of their availability to activate the electronic platforms and the specialists' attitudes on activating their use in teaching according to Quality Criteria . Determining the electronic educational platforms program, their applications, and the most important advantages in contemporary education and learning . Piloting the opinions of mathematics students to identify the advantages of the electronic educational platforms program in the teaching and learning process from their point of view . Spotting the light on the difficulties facing mathematics students' section when applying the electronic platforms program in teaching and learning .Identifying the impact of demographic factors when applying the electronic platforms program in the teaching and learning process. Determining the habits of the mind that can be developed among mathematics students (Zidan, 2005; Morgan, 2015; Mahdi, 2017). Identifying the effectiveness of teaching using electronic educational platforms in developing the concepts of algebra among students of mathematics section. Presenting a perception of teaching the Algebra course to mathematics students using electronic educational platforms, the initial hypothesis was to repeat previous studies and research that showed that training on electronic learning platforms is superior to practicing the usual methods in subsequent tests. Therefore, we tested four hypotheses.

- 3.1 There is a statistically significant difference at the level ($\alpha \leq 0, 01$) among the mean scores of the experimental and the control group students in the posttest of the habits of mind in favor of the experimental group.
- 3.2 There is a statistically significant difference at the level ($\alpha \leq 0, 01$) among the mean scores of the experimental and the control group students in the posttest of algebraic concepts in favor of the experimental group.
- 3.3 There is a statistically significant difference at the level ($\alpha \leq 0, 01$) among the mean scores of the experimental and the control group students in the posttest of learning transmission in favor of the experimental group.
- 3.4 The electronic educational platforms actively contribute to the development of habits of mind, algebraic concepts and the transmission of the learning effect, as measured by the effect size " η^2 ".

3. Method

3.1. PARTICIPANTS

The research sample included all university student's mathematics section, and the two researchers selected (445) male and female students as a basic sample representing the community of the research sample.

3.2. MATERIALS AND design

4.2.1 Preparing a list that includes the habits of the mind for the algebraic concepts, the main processes that make up them and the procedural indicators that indicate them: The current research includes (5) habits and the main processes that make up them, N= (17) processes, by reviewing many researches and studies that dealt with the compulsive habits of the mind, and the list was formed. From (46) performance indicators.

4.2.2 Electronic educational platforms: The main portal is the electronic educational platforms (Blackboard), (WebEx), which crystallized into three main questions: Where am I now (current student level)? : Provide a clear vision of learning objectives in mathematics, where am I Going (Required Level)? : Teaching

students the algebraic habits of the mind and preparing goals for the next step, How can I bridge the gap between current and desired level?: Designing focused and e-learning instruction, providing students with opportunities to follow, reflect, and share the progress of their learning.

4.2.3 Preparing the teacher's guide: This requires the following procedures: Determining the length of time required to teach algebraic concepts (by lecture and time), The teaching of algebra at the university level must be identical to the reality of mathematics, Modifying methods of teaching algebraic concepts, whereby students are indulging in procedural knowledge and habits of mind in order to undertake research, problem-solving and scientific thinking, Changing the perception of the goals of education so that it seeks to achieve an understanding of algebraic concepts, habits of mind and technology for all educational groups and not for a specific group, The student is expected to learn it in the context of the algebraic and technical habits of mind, Planning the lesson flow, In the light of the Jury's suggestions, the formulation of the guide was modified as an outcome of the study.

3.3. THE Algebraic Habits SCALE

4.3.1 Determining the objective of the scale: The scale aimed to investigate the level of students' practice of the algebraic habits of mind in terms of how to deal with them in a strategic and organized manner, and to search for and use mathematical structures, and to determine the level of practicing the habits of the mind.

4.3.2 Determining the dimensions of the scale: The habits of the algebraic mind (5) were identified, the subject of the study (describing repeated inference, perseverance with unfamiliar problems, searching for and using the algebraic concept, using appropriate tools electronically, being careful of accurate communication).

4.3.3 Formulating the scale vocabulary in its initial form: *The two researchers relied, in preparing and designing the research tool, on a set of different sources and experiences, including previous studies and research, training programs, and the researchers' experience.* From the above, a list of habits of mind was reached for the development of algebraic concepts and their performance indicators, in its initial form and it contains (26) performance indicators in light of teaching algebra, and these indicators are considered as scale phrases, as they were formulated in procedural statements, taking into account the following That the statement is observable and measurable, The phrase includes a behavioral performance, Can be measured objectively without bias and easily, The phrase appears accurately while the teacher is implementing the teaching process.

4.3.4 Drafting the scale instructions : The aim of formulating the scale instructions as they express basic instructions that enable monitoring the availability of skill in the performance indicators for the teacher during the implementation of the lesson accurately and objectively.

4.3.5 Determining the validity of the scale: To ensure the validity of the scale, the two researchers presented it to a jury (32) and experts in the field of education (18) experts, and the scale was approved by more than (95%) of the referees regarding its dimensions and expressions, and the purpose was to express opinions on Appropriateness of the scale phrases for the research topic, The suitability of the performance indicators for the requirements included in each dimension, The accuracy and integrity of the phrase spelling and linguistically, Estimate the degree of need for each phrase.

4.3.6 The Final Form of the Scale: In light of the jury's suggestions and modifications, the two researchers formed the scale, which included in its final form (5) main dimensions, (17) sub-clauses.

4.3.7 Reliability of the Scale: A survey experiment of the scale was conducted on a sample of university mathematics students, and the meta-characteristics of it were verified, including the calculation of reliability using the Cronbach's alpha coefficient, which reached (0.842) and validated the subjective content. As well as an approximate determination of the test time.

4.3.8 Method of Rating Scores in the Scale: The scale in its final form consists of (17) sub-clauses related to the algebraic habits of mind, representing a three Likert scale, and the grades are given for responding to this grade as follows: 3 = large, 2 = medium, 1 = weak, so the scores on the scale range from (17-51). To judge the degree of practice, the scores were converted into a three Likert scale to judge the arithmetic averages as follows: (1 - 1.66) a low score, from (1.67 to 2.33) a medium score, (2,34 - 3) A high score (El-Sherbiny, 2007, 101).

3.4. Algebraic Concepts Test

4.4.1 The objective of the test: The aim of the test is to measure the algebraic concepts prescribed for university students and their development, according to the following steps: Analysis of the book units scheduled for university students, Classifying the concepts mentioned in the book into concepts such as tribal requirements, and posterior concepts, Survey of theoretical literature from local and foreign research and studies related to testing the development of algebraic concepts, Using global websites specialized in mathematics testing, such as (WWW.testdesigner.com) and Study samples for tests in measuring and developing algebraic concepts.

4.4.2 Formulation of test phrases: A set of phrases were developed that fit the different dimensions of the test, taking into account that they are appropriate for the level of university students, and the vocabulary was

formulated in the form of multiple-choice questions, and there were (30) phrases in the initial image of the test.

4.4.3 Validity of the test: The test was applied to the same previous piloting sample, then the Cronbach's alpha equation was used to calculate the test reliability coefficient, and found that it was equal to (0.883), which is a relatively high stability coefficient, which indicates the possibility of its use and confidence in its results.

4.4.4 Verifying the validity of the test: Use the validity of the content to determine the validity of the test for what it was designed to measure, by presenting the test in its initial form to a jury to ensure that the test is related to the goal for which it was prepared, and its suitability for the level of university students. In the light of their opinions and observations, it was done. Making some necessary adjustments, and then the test took its final form, and became applicable to the study sample. The test included in its final form (25) statements, and the final score of the test (50) marks.

4.4.5 Determining the test time: The test time was calculated by calculating the time spent by each student in the answers to the test, then calculating the average times of the piloting sample students on the test. It was found that the appropriate time for the test is (60) minutes.

3.5. Learning Effect Transmission Test

The transfer of the effect of learning test was built into the scheduled algebra content on university students, according to the following steps:

4.5.1 Formulating the behavioral concepts. The content of the Algebra was analyzed, and the behavioral goals defined therein, were distributed to the cognitive domain levels of Bloom's advanced classification.

4.5.2 Preparing a table of specifications for the transmission of the learning effect to determine the content of the test, with the aim of linking the objectives to the content, knowing the relative importance, and the balance between the objectives and all their levels and concepts in the Algebra book, and distributing them on the test.

4.5.3 Formulation the test phrases: The test questions were formulated in the manner of essay questions, and there were (20) statements that measure students' abilities to apply concepts and acquired knowledge in new situations and problems for all algebraic concepts mentioned in the book.

4.5.4 Reliability of the test: The test was applied to the same piloting sample, then the Coder-Richardson equation (KR-20) was used to calculate the test reliability coefficient, and it was re-applied to the same sample with an interval of two weeks, and it was found to be equal to (0.903), which is a relatively high stability coefficient. , And that the repetition constant was its value (0.86). This is an indication of the quality of the test as a tool for the current study, indicating its usability and confidence in its results.

4.5.5 Verifying the validity of the test: the validity of the content was used to determine the validity of the test for what it was designed to measure, by presenting the test in its initial form to a jury from Saudi and Arab universities to ensure that the test is related to the goal for which it was prepared, and its suitability to the level of university students, and in In light of their suggestions, necessary adjustments were made, and then the test took its final form: (45) statements, and the final score of the test was (90) marks.

4.5.6 Determining the test time: The test time was calculated by calculating the time that each student took to answer the test, then calculating the average times of the exploratory sample students on the test. It was found that the appropriate time for the test is (90) minutes.

3.6. The Experimental Field Study

4.6.1 Applying algebraic concepts test and the habits of mind test to the students of the experimental and control groups to determine the actual level before the experiment.

4.6.2 Teaching the subjects of algebra prescribed to university students according to electronic learning platforms according to the quality standards of the experimental group, and to the students of the control group in the usual way.

4.6.3 Applying research tools and post-testing the transmission of the learning effect on students of the experimental and control groups.

4.6.4 Collecting the data, analyzing them statistically, drawing conclusions, discussing and interpreting them in light of the results.

3.7. DATA ANALYSES, AN overview

The researchers applied the tools to the students of the two groups of research, and monitored and processed the data statistically to confirm the validity of the hypotheses. The t-test was used for independent samples that are not related, and the ETA square calculation (η^2) was used to calculate the size of the effect of the independent variable on the dependent variables, using the program version 25 (SPSS V25).

4. Results

5.1 Verifying the validity of the first hypothesis which state : “There is a statistically significant difference at the level of ($0.01 \geq \alpha$) between the mean scores of the students of the experimental and control groups in the post application of the Habits of Mind Scale in favor of the scores of the experimental group”. To verify the validity of the first hypothesis. Means, Standard deviations, and a "t" test was used to calculate

the significance of the difference between the averages. (η^2) was also used to indicate the size of the effect, to find out how strong the influence of (d) the independent variable (platforms) on the dependent variable (habits of mind). Table No. (2) Showed the results of validating the first hypothesis.

Table (2)

Showed the results of the (T-test) to identify the significance of the difference between the mean scores of the students of the experimental and control groups, and the size of the effect in the post application of the Habits of Mind Scale.

Indicators	Group	Mean	S.D.	df	T - value	Sig. (0.01)	η^2	(d)
Description of repeated inferences	Exp.	8.39	.72	443	20.02	Sig.	0.47	0.95
	Con.	5.54	1.40					
Perseverance with unfamiliar problems	Exp.	10.44	1.20	443	19.82	Sig.	0.46	0.94
	Con.	7.20	1.35					
Find and use the algebraic concept	Exp.	10.43	1.05	443	27.34	Sig.	0.62	1.29
	Con.	6.00	1.46					
Use the appropriate tools electronically	Exp.	7.30	.67	443	23.36	Sig.	0.55	1.10
	Con.	4.82	.97					
Keep the accuracy of communication	Exp.	8.57	1.07	443	29.96	Sig.	0.67	1.42
	Con.	5.16	.67					
The scale as a whole	Exp.	45.15	1.99	443	45.01	Sig.	0.82	2.13
	Con.	28.72	3.52					

It is noticed from Table (2) that there is a statistically significant difference between the mean scores of the students of the experimental and control groups in the post- application of the Habits of Mind Scale in favor of the scores of the experimental group that studied the course using electronic platforms. This indicates the high level of some habits of mind among the experimental group. Thus, it leads to accept this hypothesis.

This confirms the effectiveness of the independent variable (electronic learning platforms) with a strong impact on the dependent variable (habits of mind), and its sub-components, where the ratio was between (0.94 - 1.42), and for the scale as a whole, the degree of effect (d) reached (2.13). This indicates that the use of electronic educational platforms Electronic has a great effect on developing some habits of mind among students of the experimental group.

The researchers attribute this result to the fact that the university stage is an essential stage in the educational process, and therefore it requires a lot of attention, accuracy and implementation by those responsible for the educational process as a whole and the training of faculty members on electronic platforms, and the most important way for this is to provide an educational environment that is flexible in terms of time and place, And using more than one way to display scientific content and knowledge related to the course, providing more than one source for obtaining information and mathematical content via internet networks, increasing the space for students' participation in educational activities and training, exchanging experiences, providing opportunities for communication between students to discuss the prescribed topics, and this result can also be traced back to training students in habits of mind and providing a useful amount of knowledge that was presented through electronic learning platforms in the Algebra course.

5.2 Verifying the validity of the second hypothesis: To verify the validity of the second hypothesis, which states: "There is a statistically significant difference at the level of (0.01) between the mean scores of the students of the experimental and control groups in the post-application of the test of algebraic concepts in favor of the experimental group. To verify the validity of the second hypothesis, appropriate statistical parameters were used, such as: Means, Standard deviations, and a "t" test to calculate the significance of the difference between the averages. (2η) has also been used to indicate the size of the effect, to find out the strength of the influence of (d) the independent variable (electronic educational platforms) on the dependent variable (algebraic concepts). Table No. (3) Showed the results of validating the second hypothesis.

Table (3)

Indicated the results of the T-test to calculate the significance of the difference between the mean scores of the students of the experimental and control groups and the size of the effect in the post-application of the algebraic concepts test.

Indicator	Group	Means	S.D.	df	T- value	Sig. (0.01)	η^2	d
Algebraic concepts	Exp.	48.59	1.186	443	27.73	Sig.	0.63	1.317
	Cont.	37.91	4.104					

It is noticed from Table (3) that there was a statistically significant difference between the mean scores of the students of the experimental and control groups in the post-application of the algebraic concepts test, and that this difference is in favor of the scores of the experimental group that studied the course using electronic learning platforms. This indicates the high level of some algebraic concepts among the experimental group students, which leads to the acceptance of this hypothesis.

This confirms the effectiveness of the independent variable (electronic educational platforms), which has a

Group	N.	Pre		Post	
		S.D.	Mean	S.D.	Mean
Exp.	223	13.67	19.73	16.62	74.93
Con.	222	12.69	18.37	20.12	46.78

strong impact on the dependent variable (algebraic concepts), as the (d) reached (1.317), and this indicates that the use of the electronic educational platforms had a significant impact on the development of some algebraic concepts among students of the experimental group.

5.3 Verifying the validity of the third hypothesis: The third hypothesis is valid, which states that: “There was a statistically significant difference at (0.01) level between the mean scores of the experimental and control group in the post-application of the postponed achievement test (Learning Effect Transmission)” in favor of the experimental group. To verify the validity of the third hypothesis, Mean scores and Standard deviations, the pre/post-application of the test (transmission of learning effect) was used among university students. Table No. (4) Shows the results of validating the third hypothesis

Table (4)

Shows the mean scores and standard deviations of the learning effect transmission test for university students for pre/post-application according to the teaching variable in the electronic educational platforms

It is noticed from Table (4) that there is a significant difference between the mean scores and the standard deviation of the university students' performance in the post-measurement learning effect transmission test resulting from the difference in the teaching approach. To verify the essence of this difference using the analysis of covariance, the homogeneity of the tendency was verified by determining what interaction between the teaching entrance and the pre-learning transmission test, where the result was not statistically significant, and accordingly the (ANCOVA) post-measurement analysis was performed to test the transmission of the learning effect according to the electronic educational platforms after neutralizing the effect of the pre-measurement for them. Table No. (5) Showed results of the verification.

Table (5)

Showed an analysis of common variance (ANCOVA) for the students' performance on the Test of transmission learning effect according to the electronic educational platforms after neutralizing the effect of students' performance on the pretest

Variance	Sum	df	Average of Sum	“F” Value	Sig.	(η^2)
Pre-teaching	10681.993	1	10681.997	60.798	0.000	0.476
Teaching by platforms	8139.711	1	8139.782	46.573	0.000	0.409
Error	11788.581	242	179.618			
Total Rate	31659.253	244				

It is evident from Table (5) that there was a statistically significant difference at the level (0.01) between the two means of the post-measurement of the transmission of the learning effect of university students attributed to the electronic educational platforms. To determine in favor of either of the two study groups, the difference was clear. The modified mean was calculated for the post-measurement of the transmission of the learning effect of university students according to the electronic educational platforms and their standard errors, Table No. (6) Showed these results.

Table (6)

The Means of the modified performance of university students on the post-measurement learning effect transmission test and its standard errors according to the independent variable (electronic educational platforms).

It is evident from Table (6) that the clear difference was in favor of the experimental group students who studied using electronic educational platforms compared to the control group students who studied in the regular way. This means that there is a high impact of the independent variable (electronic educational platforms) on the transmission of the learning effect among university students.

5. Discussion

The results showed the main role of electronic educational platforms as a learning environment for habits of the mind and the development of algebraic concepts and a participatory communicative environment in university education. This may be due to the fact that:

- The importance of electronic platforms stems from the tools they provide to the educational process in terms of obtaining educational information easily, by providing a multi-source, multimedia and high-tech educational environment, which leads to increasing the efficiency and improving the level of learning, and developing the habits of mind for students in various scientific activities and tasks.
- Electronic platforms allow students to participate in performance. It is in the interest of students to participate in the production of educational content, provide opportunities for students to watch the work of their groups, formulate ideas with their own thinking styles and opinions, evaluate their work, and raise the level of students' performance by increasing their motivation towards learning, and increasing positive interaction for participatory work as file download capacity increases.
- The electronic platforms constitute an accessible way for every student to use, whereby every student affiliated with the university can, through the username and password, enter the platform and see all its content and continuous interaction through an application on the smartphone, while providing continuous notifications when any New content or post.
- The electronic platforms facilitate and activate the process of communication within the environment of classroom interaction between students themselves, and between students and staff through discussion rooms, facilitating the evaluation of students' work, reviewing their duties and providing immediate feedback to them. Parents can also see the evaluation of their children's duties and receive member notifications teaching staff about their level.

6. Conclusion

- The necessity of the university's interest in providing programs and activities that support students' habits of mind and enhance students' responses and participation.
- The university adopts the production of academic curricula, especially mathematics, in an electronic form that takes into account the technical and educational quality standards, and allocates a special budget for it.
- Conducting a piloting survey of students affiliated with electronic learning platforms before submitting the course in order to identify their needs.
- Providing electronic learning platforms to provide university courses, especially mathematics, that encourage students to learn and participate in educational societies via the web.
- The need to pay attention to the field of analyzing the informative content of the Algebra and the habits of mind according to quality criteria.
- The necessity to focus on the importance of using electronic platforms as a modern teaching method that

Teaching Approach	Modified Mean	Standard Error
Electronic Educational Platforms	72.752	2.346
Regular method	45.634	2.194

has many advantages in terms of increasing motivation, uniqueness of education and collaborative participation.

- The necessity to address the reality related to the informative content of the mathematics curriculum on the e-learning platforms by analyzing and linking to the practical reality, thus contributing to highlighting the advantages and disadvantages of these platforms and measuring the quality of each.
- The need to direct the attention of specialists and officials to the most important strengths related to e-learning platforms in order to support them, and weaknesses in order to correct and amend them in a way that contributes to strengthening the information content of the specialty.
- The necessity of spreading information awareness of the specialization and ensuring the development of society and encouraging the acquisition of knowledge for life.

- The necessity to strive towards improving the level of university education by deepening scientific knowledge about the specialization.
- Issuing and modifying standards and best practices in the specialization (Theory and practice).
- Encouraging the provision of assistance through technical expertise, developing international technical cooperation initiatives, and making use of the experiences and best practices of global educational institutions.
- Encouraging students to consciously exercise rights and duties within and outside the university framework, and directing all activities and lectures to educate students intellectually and socially.
- Working to facilitate the use of electronic educational platforms and educate students on easy ways to benefit from them.
- Training faculty members in using electronic learning platforms, and giving more attention to employing open and closed platforms in university.
- Providing technical, technological and material support to use the electronic learning platforms in an easier way for students.
- Overcoming the obstacles facing the optimization of the electronic learning platforms for educational purposes.

7. Declarations of interest

None.

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